

Abuse of Dominance in the Digital Market:
Analysis of the Amazon and Flipkart v. CCI Case

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Abstract

Abuse of dominance in the digital market, often referred to as antitrust or competition law violations, is a topic of increasing concern and regulatory focus in many countries around the world. Due to the absence of a specialised Act for Digital Competition, the Competition Act, 2002, deals with the regulation of any anti-competitive behaviour in the Digital Sphere in India. The Competition Commission of India (CCI) is the regulatory authority responsible for enforcing competition law in the country. Digital markets are characterised by a few dominant players who hold significant market power, and the abuse of this power can harm competition, consumers, and innovation. This paper aims to analyse how the dominant players of the Digital Market are misusing their position of Dominance and practising Anti-Competitive Behaviours. The paper provides a critical analysis of the current situation while linking it with the landmark case of the Delhi Vyapar Mahasangh v. Amazon & Flipkart case, where the Competition Commission of India (CCI) initiated an investigation into the alleged abuse of dominance and anti-competitive agreements by Amazon and Flipkart. This paper also analyses the implications of the CCI's intervention and evaluates the legal framework governing abuse of dominance in digital markets.

Keywords: Abuse, Dominance, E-commerce, Competition, Digital Market, Competition Commission of India

Introduction

The use of the internet and the growth of technology have seen a surprisingly high surge in the last decade, especially in the previous few years. Currently, there is hardly anyone who is not influenced by the existence of the internet and social media. Mostly, everyone is found to be “online” these days, either through social media, reading news, availing online services or shopping using various e-commerce platforms. More than four billion people worldwide, out of the total population of seven billion, use the Internet, and this pace shows no indications of mellowing down.¹ This technological advancement has brought with it massive amounts of changes and evolution in the traditional methods of conducting business.

¹ Amazon Anti-Competition Law in the International Political Economy, By Fajar Purnomo Adi. Proceedings of the Asia-Pacific Research in Social Sciences and Humanities Universitas Indonesia

A new method of conducting business by way of electronic or digital means has evolved in the recent past, that is, the E-Commerce revolution. The digitalisation of business has led to changes in the way a business used to function traditionally. The key players in bringing this transformation are the digital platforms such as Amazon, Flipkart, Myntra and others, that facilitate online shopping. Its rapid growth and dependence of people on these platforms are making them the “fourth industrial revolution”.² Its increased popularity is owing to the benefits provided to the consumers by making products and services available at their doorsteps, making their lives quick and convenient.

The soaring expansion of the digital platforms is evident from the advancements in cloud computing, mobile and analytics, and other such new technologies, that is essential for bringing the vast number of consumers and providers together. The digital platforms are creating various markets on an immensely huge scale and paving the path for partnerships between companies from different industries, and creating a whole new line of products and services. The products and services which were unimaginable to be provided at your doorstep are now available at the tap of your fingers. Any product, ranging from clothes, makeup, shoes, to accessories for your pets, is available easily. Similarly, services like booking cabs and cleaning services can be done hassle-free, all due to digitisation.

Impact of Digitisation on the Traditional Market System

Digitisation has brought substantial changes to the lives of people through the introduction of digital platforms. Digital platforms have opened up a new market and industry that is different to the traditional ways of business market and industry. This new industry has paved the way for the digital economy, which is based on technology that uses data processing and communication for its business. The E-Commerce sector in India is driven by expanding digital infrastructure, increasing consumer wealth, and rising penetration in tier-2 and tier-3 cities. The E-Commerce

Conference (APRISH 2019). *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 558.

² Kore, S., & Yadav, J. (2020). Attempt to Monopolisation and Digital Markets: Enforcement Gap. *Competition Commission of India Journal on Competition Law and Policy*, 1, 103–122. <https://doi.org/10.54425/ccijoclp.v1.12>

market is expected to grow from US\$ 123 billion in FY24 to US\$ 292.3 billion by FY28 at a CAGR of 18.7%, and further to US\$ 325 billion by 2030. The quick commerce industry is anticipated to touch US\$ 5 billion by FY25 and US\$ 9.9 billion by FY29, while the B2B e-marketplace is estimated to reach US\$ 200 billion by 2030. The Government e-Marketplace (GeM) has already surpassed last year's GMV of Rs. 4 lakh crore within just 10 months of FY25. India has the third-largest online shopper base globally and is expected to grow from 150 million in FY21 to 350 million by FY26. Despite e-commerce exports currently at US\$ 2 billion, India has significant room to expand its presence in the projected US\$ 8 trillion global B2C market by 2030.³ These recent developments have made India emerge as an eminent market player in the digital platform industry, among others in the world.

The E-Commerce giants like Amazon and Flipkart have also emerged as key market players, giving opportunities to small local businesses and home businesses a platform for their products, while also posing a threat to the offline retailers and businesses to survive in the market. Thus, the digitalisation has brought major changes in the traditional business economy and in the functioning of these traditional business models. Although the benefits of digital platforms are undeniable, the potential competitive concerns that they can pose are not. The players in the digital market are continuously competing with each other to gain consumers for their products and services. There is a high possibility that market giants like Amazon and Flipkart might hold a dominant position in a specific market by providing deep discounts to their consumers, controlling the data, having exclusive agreements with dealers and suppliers, etc. Therefore, arises the necessity for regulations to maintain fair competition in the market.⁴

The regulatory authority for competition policies in India, the Competition Commission of India (CCI), received a series of complaints against E-Commerce platforms like Amazon & Flipkart, complaining about abuse of dominant position. According to Forrester Research, Flipkart's market share was 31.9% by October 2020 — making it the largest online retailer in India, and Amazon

³ E-commerce Industry in India; Blog in India Brand Equity Foundation, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India. <https://www.ibef.org/industry/ecommerce>

⁴ Daniel Mandrescu, EU competition law and the digital economy: protecting free and fair competition in an age of technological (R) evolution, Vol 3, 2020, eleven international publishing, pp.1-3

had a market share of 31.2%.⁵ In January 2020, these two renowned e-commerce giants, Flipkart Internet Services Pvt. Ltd. (Flipkart) and Amazon Seller Services Pvt. Ltd. (Amazon) were involved in a case filed by Delhi VyaparMahasangh (DVM) at the Competition Commission of India (CCI) alleging business malpractices. DVM is a society of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) traders dealing in smartphones and related accessories registered under the Societies Registration Act, 1860 and affiliated to Confederation of All India Traders (CAIT). These complaints emphasised the need to maintain equilibrium in the present market dynamics in order to protect the interests of the consumers and other stakeholders in the market.

The competition laws and regulations believe in a consumer welfare approach, but with the growing competition concerns in the digital market, the new entrants need assurance that they can enter the market without any barriers from the dominant market players. The competition policies must ensure a free and fair digital market with a variety of choices in products and services for the consumers, thus promoting healthy competition.⁶ The CCI plays an important role in ensuring a balance is maintained in the market by ensuring economic efficiency, which results in foreign investments in the digital sector and incentivising technological innovation for upscaling the digital market.⁷ In order to maintain healthy competition among market players, it is of utmost importance that the activities of dominant players like Amazon and Flipkart are kept under surveillance to ensure that there is no abuse of dominant position.

Abuse of Dominance in the Digital Market

The competition regime in India works towards keeping the competition alive in the market by creating free space for new entrants and promoting innovation, choice and fair pricing.⁸ In this context, abuse of dominance refers to the actions of dominant players of the market that exploit their dominant position in the relevant market to harm competition, consumers or other

⁵ Gabriela Barkho, How the Pandemic Strengthened Walmart-Owned Flipkart's Marketshare, ModernRetail. <https://www.modernretail.co/platforms/how-the-pandemic-strengthened-walmart-ownedflipkarts-marketshare/>.

⁶ Combating abuse of dominance in digital markets: Study from the perspective of EU and India - By Nirmala Mahaveer Patil. Lund University, School of Economics and Management.

⁷ Padmavathy Nehru, DIGITAL ECONOMY & COMPETITION LAW: A CONUNDRUM, 2 IJLR 22, 2022

⁸ DIGITAL ECONOMY & COMPETITION LAW: A CONUNDRUM - by Aryan Mohindroo and Rajat Mohindroo. INDIAN COMPETITION LAW REVIEW Volume 3, May 2018, pp 82-103

stakeholders and gain an unfair advantage over competitors. These acts by dominant players can harm the objectives of fair competition and hinder the growth of a market and consumer interests. As per the European Court of Justice, a dominant market position has been defined as:

“A position of economic strength enjoyed by an undertaking which enables it to prevent effective competition being maintained on the relevant market by affording it the power to behave to an appreciable extent independently of its competitors, customers and ultimately of consumers.”⁹

A prerequisite for determining whether a market player holds a dominant position is that it must behave to an appreciable degree independently of its competitors and consumers. The dominant position of a player is determined by using quantitative measures of market shares, price levels, concentration ratios or profit margins without realising some of these indicators can be defined only when the market remains static.¹⁰ However, the same cannot be used for the digital market, due to its dynamic nature. Hence, it becomes a challenge to differentiate between anti-competitive practices in the digital market from its natural course of business strategies.¹¹ Therefore, abuse of dominance is the improper or excessive use of a dominant position by a player in the market, which has an appreciable adverse effect on competition in the market. However, dominance by itself is not bad per se, but the abuse of this dominance is bad. The law does not penalise being in a dominant position rather, it prohibits abuse of such dominance to gain undue advantage.

Section 4 of the Competition Act, 2002 deals with abuse of dominant position and addresses provisions for anti-competitive behaviour by dominant enterprises¹² or groups¹³. It provides conditions under which their conduct can be considered to be an abuse of dominant position and a

⁹ Case C-27/76, United Brands Company and United Brands Continental BV v Commission of the European Communities, 1978 ECR 207; Case C-85/76, Hoffmann-La Roche & Co. AG v Commission of the European Communities, 1979 ECR 461.

¹⁰ Organisation of Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), The Digital Economy (Feb. 7, 2013), <http://www.oecd.org/daf/competition/The-Digital-Economy-2012.pdf>

¹¹ Study of the Policy Department A: Economic and Scientific Policy on Challenges for Competition Policy in a Digitalised Economy (Jul.

2015), http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2015/542235/IPOL_STU%282015%29542235_EN.pdf

¹² Section 2 (h) Competition Act 2002

¹³ The term ‘Group’ is mentioned in explanation (b) of Section 5 of Competition Act 2002 that, two or more enterprises directly or indirectly are in position to exercise 26% or more of voting rights in other enterprise or appoints more than 50 % of board of Directors or controls management & affairs of other enterprise.

violation of the provisions of the Act. Section 4(1) specifically prohibits abuse of dominant position by an enterprise or group. Section 4(2)¹⁴ provides for the following conditions that constitute abuse of dominant position:¹⁵

1. Direct or indirect imposition of unfair, discriminatory conditions or price (which includes predatory price) in the purchase or sale of goods or services. However, a discriminatory condition or price adopted to serve competition is permitted,
2. Acts which restrict production and cause adverse effects to technical or scientific development in relation to goods or services,
3. Practices, amounting to a denial of market access,
4. Concluding a contract subject to acceptance of supplementary obligations which have no connection with the subject matter of the contract,
5. Abusing its dominant position in one relevant market for the purpose of entering another relevant market.

Thus, acts of causing harm to entry, restricting production or development, price discrimination, denial of market access, and unfair conditions imposed in transactions amount to abuse of dominant position. However, there's no presence of separate legal provision for dealing with abuse of competition in digital markets.

The digital markets are characterised by a few dominant players who hold significant market power, and the abuse of this power can harm competition, consumers, and innovation. Dominant platforms like Amazon and Flipkart seek to expand their businesses vertically in upstream and downstream markets and compete with merchants or app developers using their platforms. This expansion enhances their ability to accumulate more data and boost their competitiveness.¹⁶ This situation can, at any time, allow for abusive and exclusionary behaviour by these dominant

¹⁴ Section 4(2) Competition Act 2002

¹⁵ Combating abuse of dominance in digital markets: Study from the perspective of EU and India - By Nirmala Mahaveer Patil. Lund University, School of Economics and Management.

¹⁶ UNITED NATIONS CONFERENCE ON TRADE & DEVELOPMENT 2019, https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/ciclpd54_en.pdf

platforms. Digital monopolies, barriers to market entry for new entrants, and preemptive mergers constitute abuse of a dominant position.¹⁷

In the context of abuse of dominance in digital markets, establishing a prima facie case is paramount to competition law enforcement. A prima facie case is the initial evidence that, if unrebutted, would be sufficient to prove a particular legal claim or violation. Section 26 of the Competition Act gives authority to initiate investigations by the Competition Commission of India (CCI) into alleged anti-competitive practices, only if there exists a prima facie case made with reference to material produced before it. CCI has often closed preliminary cases as they do not want to interfere with innovative techniques that are applied in the digital market to attract buyers in the economy. In the case of *Vinod Kumar Gupta v WhatsApp*¹⁸, the court recognised that even though there is a dominant position, there's no abuse of such dominance as seen in the Prima Facie Case. Thus, making the role of 'Prima Facie' Case very important for understanding abuse in the digital market economy.

In relation to such abuse of dominance, two giants of the digital market, Amazon & Flipkart, were highly scrutinised by the CCI. In January 2020, Delhi VyaparMahasangh (DVM) filed a case against Flipkart Internet Services Pvt. Ltd. (Flipkart) and Amazon Seller Services Pvt. Ltd. (Amazon) before the CCI, alleging that these two entities have been involved in anti-competitive practices that are detrimental to the interests of the consumers. This case became the centre for a much larger discussion, that is, the need for a separate legal framework or provisions under the existing act to deal with growing competitive concerns regarding the digital market. It also raised questions about whether such e-commerce giants like Amazon and Flipkart are abusing their dominant position under the garb of innovation and the dynamic nature of the digital market.

¹⁷ RICHARD WHISH & DAVID BAILEY, *COMPETITION LAW 760* (Oxford University Press 2012).

¹⁸ Case No. 99 of 2016

Critical Analysis - Amazon, Flipkart V. CCI, 2020

Facts of the Case

The case of *Amazon, Flipkart v. CCI*¹⁹, originated from a complaint filed by Delhi VyaparMahasangh (DVM), a trade association representing small and medium enterprises and businesses. The complaint was filed before the CCI, under Section 19(1) of the Competition Act 2002, alleging that the E-Commerce giants, Amazon and Flipkart, engaged in vertical agreements with preferred traders and excluded non-preferred traders from fair competition on their respective platforms. The complaint also alleged violations of competition laws relating to anti-competitive agreements under Section 3(4) read with Section 3(1) and Section 4(2) read with Section 4(1), that is, abuse of dominance. They argued that these anti-competitive practices had an appreciable adverse effect on the competition in the digital market and affected the interests of the consumers by limiting their choices. The main issues alleged by DVM were in relation to preferential listing, deep discounting, exclusive agreements, and preferred sellers.

Subsequent to the complaint, CCI directed the Director General (DG) to probe an investigation under Section 26(1) of the Competition Act, 2002. However, this investigation ordered by CCI was challenged by Amazon before the Karnataka High Court, which resulted in a temporary stay on the investigation. Following this stay order, the CCI approached the Supreme Court to overturn it, however, the Apex court referred the case back to the Karnataka High Court. Finally, in June 2021, the Karnataka High Court lifted the stay, allowing the CCI to proceed with its investigation into Amazon and Flipkart's alleged anti-competitive practices.

Allegations against Amazon & Flipkart

1. Preferential Listing: It was accused that Amazon was favouring sellers like Cloudtail and Appario Retail by giving their products more significance and prominence in search results. As per allegations made, it was stated that products with similar ratings appeared later in search rankings, while the initial pages were dominated by preferred sellers. Similarly,

¹⁹ Amazon Seller Services Private Limited vs Competition Commission of India, W.P. No. 3363 of 2020 & W.P. No. 4334 of 2020 (Karnataka High Court, June 11, 2021); Case No. 40 of 2019

Flipkart was alleged to have used the term "Assured" to highlight products from its preferred sellers, thereby influencing customer choices.

2. **Deep Discounting:** The complaint alleged that preferred sellers were incentivised to offer predatory pricing, making it difficult for small businesses to compete. Flipkart allegedly followed a discounting model favouring sellers like Omnitech Retail and WS Retail, which was detrimental to non-preferred sellers.
3. **Exclusive Tie-Ups:** It was claimed that deep discounting and preferential listings led to de facto exclusivity, where Amazon and Flipkart entered into agreements with smartphone brands to launch exclusive products, preventing smaller sellers from accessing and selling those devices.
4. **Preferential Treatment to Select Sellers:** Although the platforms are open to all, DVM alleged that they strategically benefit their preferred sellers, failing to maintain neutrality. Instead of fostering equal competition, they were accused of promoting private labels owned by Amazon and Flipkart.

Issues addressed in the case

1. Whether the order passed by the CCI directing investigation under Section 26(1) of the Competition Act, 2002, against Amazon and Flipkart, requires prior notice and is valid in light of the prima facie findings?
2. Whether the practices of deep discounting, preferential listing, and promotion of private labels by Amazon and Flipkart result in market foreclosure and create entry barriers for non-preferred sellers in violation of Section 3(1) of the Competition Act, 2002?
3. Whether the exclusive arrangements between Amazon/Flipkart and select smartphone brands/sellers amount to anti-competitive vertical agreements under Section 3(4) of the Competition Act, 2002?

Ruling by the Karnataka High Court

The Karnataka High Court held that the CCI could establish a prima facie case under Section 3(1) read with Section 3(4) of the Act against the e-commerce giants, Amazon and Flipkart. It further noted that the alleged anti-competitive practices of exclusive tie-ups, deep discounting, preferential listings, and promotion of private labels could potentially result in an appreciable adverse effect on competition in the digital market. The CCI directed the DG to conduct a detailed investigation into the conduct of Amazon and Flipkart under Section 26(1) of the Act in order to determine whether there was a violation of competition laws. It was also instructed to the DG to complete the investigation within 60 days from receipt of the order.

Further, the allegation regarding dominance was not examined under Section 4 of the Act, since the CCI clarified that joint dominance is not recognised in the current competition legislation.²⁰ It was further clarified and emphasised that these observations are not final and they are required to be backed by a proper, independent, and objective investigation by the DG, before final conclusions are drawn.

Developments after the case

Subsequent to this tussle between the E-commerce giants and CCI, the DG conducted a detailed investigation as directed into the allegations of anti-competitive conduct by Amazon and Flipkart. The investigation revealed anti-competitive conduct as alleged, that is, favouring preferred sellers, deep discounting, and exclusive tie-ups, resulting in an appreciable adverse effect on competition in the digital market. The DG submitted a detailed report of the investigation confirming that Amazon and Flipkart were in violation of competition laws. While contemplating an appropriate amount for penalties, CCI considered imposing a penalty of 10% of Amazon's global turnover, as per the competition laws of the country.

Amazon and Flipkart, aggrieved by this outcome, challenged the findings of the investigation in various High Courts across the country. They argued that the investigation lacked sufficient

²⁰ Amazon, Flipkart V. CCI, 2020: A Turning Point For Antitrust Cases In India?, Divyanshi Singhal & Ekta Agarwal, International Journal Of Advanced Legal Research Volume 1, Issue 4, June 2021, ISSN: 2582-7340

evidence to draw such conclusions and lacked procedural fairness as well. The CCI petitioned the Supreme Court to transfer all the cases to a single court. Therefore, the Apex Court²¹ in 6 January 2025, transferred multiple writ petitions pending before various High Courts across the country to the Karnataka High Court. The bench comprising Justice Abhay S. Oka and Justice Ujjal Bhuyan observed that the subject matter of these various petitions is in alignment with the ongoing case, which is being heard by the Karnataka High Court. Hence, it shall be favourable if all future petitions involving similar issues are dealt with in one court to maintain uniformity in the proceedings.²² Furthermore, the CCI also called for financial records of both the E-commerce giants to assess their market influence and determine an appropriate penalty for the violation.

Conclusion

The competition issues in the digital market and its shortcomings regarding the existing competition framework have been a topic of debate and discussion for a long. This case further led to large-scale policy reform discussions, influencing policymakers to draft stricter e-commerce regulations in India that averted such anti-competitive practices in the digital market. The investigation and subsequent legal proceedings set a precedent for future competition law enforcement in the digital economy, reinforcing the need for accountability and transparency in e-commerce operations. With ongoing hearings and regulatory changes, the case remains a significant milestone in shaping India's competition framework for online businesses, impacting future regulations on seller partnerships, pricing strategies, and competition laws. Amazon and Flipkart are indeed two major market players in the digital market and will surely safeguard their goodwill against these allegations to maintain their market dominance and share. This landmark case has been a starting point for much-needed discussions with regard to stringent competition policies to ensure a fair and open market for all in the ever-growing digital industry.

²¹ Competition Commission of India v. Clouttail India Private Limited, TP (C) No. 3364-3387/2024; Diary No. 56571/2024

²² Supreme Court Transfers Petitions Against CCI Probe Into Amazon and Flipkart to Karnataka High Court, Safiya Malik, January 12, 2025, 24Law. <https://24law.in/story/supreme-court-transfers-petitions-against-cci-probe-into-amazon-and-flipkart-to-karnataka-high-court>